

CODING, MODELING AND 3D-PRINTING TO ACHIEVE INSCRIBABILITY: AN EMBODIED MATHEMATICAL EXPERIENCE WITHIN A NEW CONCEPTUAL FIELD

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This study examines the mathematical activity of students when programming digital models for 3D printing, framed by Embodied Mathematical Thinking and Embodied Instrumentation. The challenge of fitting geometrical entities within others creates a new Conceptual Field, “Inscribability”, within which our qualitative empirical research explores how students develop embodied mental schemas, patterns and strategies when creating physical models through parametric coding and dynamic manipulation. Findings highlight how digital and physical tools mediate transitions between abstract mathematical reasoning and embodied expression, creating recursive learning cycles where each modality reinforces the other. This approach reorganizes curricular boundaries through problem-centred learning via multimodal engagement (visual, kinaesthetic, haptic) contributing to the Embodied learning in Mathematics with minimalistic digital tools.

Keywords: Embodied Mathematics, Programming, Dynamic Manipulation, Inscribability, 3d printing

INTRODUCTION

Over the past twenty years, research has vividly highlighted that dynamic manipulation of mathematical representations significantly enhances geometric reasoning and supports conjecture development (Arzarello et al., 2002; Baccaglini & Mariotti, 2010). At the same time, there is a strong trend towards introducing mathematization and modeling activities, as their educational benefits for cultivating critical thinking skills have been well documented in the literature for many years now (Blum & Niss, 1991). However, few studies examine how children use programming to model geometric concepts—a surprising gap, given the rich potential of Geometry as a particularly fertile field for creating mathematical models (Freudenthal, 1972) and for interrelated approaches that promote rich meaning-making (Kynigos & Grizioti, 2018). Geometry instruction continues to fail to take advantage of the built-in interactive capabilities of digital interfaces. It relies mainly on pre-designed visual tools (manipulative or digital), without paying sufficient attention to the dynamic creation of objects by the children themselves (Ng & Chan, 2019). While dynamic geometry software (e.g., GeoGebra) has transformed mathematics education, such tools often prioritize pre-made visualizations over student initiative, limiting students' opportunities to define, correct, and validate geometric principles through structured computational thinking. Furthermore, despite the possibilities offered by 3D design and printing technologies (Ng & Ferrara 2020; Ng & Ye, 2022), the relationship between modeling geometric concepts, dynamic manipulation, and tangible construction through 3D printing remains underexplored. Addressing this, we attempt an approach that rethinks how technology can serve conceptual mastery over procedural fluency while modeling geometrical entities, and we proceed to assemble “Inscribability” as a new Conceptual Field (Vergnaud, 2009) as described further below. This study aims to examine how dynamic manipulation of models incorporating geometric relationships, properties and invariants, can be

combined with the 3D printing process to enhance the learning experience. The objective was to answer the following questions:

1. How does the dynamic manipulation of models and the parameters that define them, as well as the materialization perspective offered by 3D printing, affect the ways in which children perceive and express Inscrivability as a relationship?
2. What embodied mental schemas do students develop during their constructions to achieve Inscrivability and how do they capture them (verbally, gesturing, symbolically)?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Embodied Mathematical Thinking & Embodied Instrumentation

Embodied Mathematical Thinking posits that mathematical meaning emerges through bodily engagement with tools and environment (Alibali & Nathan, 2011). Research confirms physical interaction (gestures, object manipulation) dynamically shapes mathematical understanding (Nemirovsky et al., 2013) with movement and cognition constituting dynamically interrelated phenomena (Abrahamson & Bakker, 2016; Roth, 2016). Research such as that of Roth & Maheux (2015) demonstrate that mathematical thinking is not limited to virtual representations but manifests itself through creative processes where body and mind work together seamlessly (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2014). Mathematical instruments thus become active systems that embody material, practical and multimodal interactions, where knowledge emerges through bodily engagement, implying transformations in children's lived experiences (Nemirovsky et al, 2020). This view challenges the traditional distinction between 'internal' knowledge and 'external' agency, positing bodily action as a component of mathematical meaning-making and practice.

The Embodied Instrumentation framework integrates Instrumental Approach and Embodied Cognition theories to examine bodily engagement in digital mathematical learning. It emphasizes the synergistic interplay between instrumentalization schemas (tool-mediated strategies) and sensorimotor schemas (bodily actions), demonstrating their co-development in mathematical cognition (Drijvers, 2019; Shvarts et al., 2021). Central to this framework is the agency of digital tools: rather than passively conveying concepts, they mediate triadic co-emergence of sensorimotor engagement, technical proficiency, and conceptual understanding. The body regulates instrumental actions (e.g., 3D model manipulation), while multimodal feedback (haptic, visual) bridges perception and abstraction. In the present study, Embodied Instrumentation is used in a dual role, providing on the one hand an instrumental perspective, focusing on how students are using the digital tools to inscribe shapes into other shapes and/or solids, and on the other hand an embodied perspective, highlighting how bodily actions (e.g., gestures, spatial navigation) and perceptual experiences (e.g., visualization of rotations) consolidate abstract concepts through physical interaction.

Conceptual Fields [CF]

The Theory of Conceptual Fields [CF] (Vergnaud, 2009) posits that mathematical concepts derive meaning and depth only within structured networks of interrelated elements arguing that a mathematical concept does not refer to just one type of situation and, conversely, that a situation cannot be analysed through just one concept. A Conceptual Field [CF] is assembled as a triad consisting of: 1) Representations (linguistic/symbolic systems) that are currently available in the subject's mental arsenal for the concept 2) Problem situations where the concept can be encountered or used and 3) Other related/affiliated concepts/meanings interconnecting

mathematical ideas. This triadic framework rejects the notion of concepts as isolated entities and, emphasizes instead, their situational emergence through meaning-making in personally relevant problem contexts, progressive stabilization via social negotiation, strategy development and adaptive schema formation through concept-field interactions.

METHODOLOGY

Assembling the CF “Inscribability”

In this study the CF “Inscribability” has been structured through the following triplet:

1. i) Representations of the children through their lived experience (how they perceive it with their own bodies and their spatial awareness) and
ii) Representations of the children being built by using the digital tools
2. Problem-activity: a design-thinking project consisting of
i) digital creation by textual coding and
ii) the physical construction (3d printable models)
3. Other related/affiliated concepts (e.g. geometry and trigonometry concepts) and students’ spatial reasoning

Figure 1: Assembling the CF “Inscribability”

MaLT2

MaLT2 (<http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/malt2/#Gr>) is a computational environment for creating and manipulating 3D dynamic digital models. It unifies multimodal representations, symbolic (Logo-like) and figural (graphical objects), and allows dynamic manipulation of the parameters of an executed process by interconnecting functionalities that interact dynamically (Kynigos & Grizioti, 2018). At the same time, it enables the changing of the viewing angle of the 3D space (Kynigos & Grizioti, 2018). It allows the user to define computational procedures (sets of commands), which, when executed, produce geometric shapes in a 3D "scene", bridging programming with mathematical concepts and mathematical formalism. The dynamic manipulation of models enables the user to introduce variables into the code and modify them through sliders, thus promoting direct monitoring of the effect of variables on graphical results, enhancing the understanding of the relationship between algebraic parameters and geometric properties.

Research Design

The present research is the pilot part of a larger design-based research (Barab & Squire, 2004) and comprised five two-hour interventions in a vocational high school in Athens. Participants included 20 students (aged 16–17) with prior Python programming experience and some basic knowledge of Algebra, Geometry, and Trigonometry. They worked in groups of 2 and 3 in the computer lab, with one computer per group. The members of each team took turns using the mouse and keyboard.

Activities

The design thinking project that was implemented in the context of this research challenged students to create functional 3D-printed objects (e.g., cable organizers, cup holders) using the MaLT2 environment. After familiarizing with MaLT2, students were given some predefined 2D models (circle, square; Figure 2) to explore, edit, and/or even use as building blocks ("building units")

for their constructions. Then groups decided what they wanted to build and defined what purpose they wanted their model to satisfy, they decided on practical issues (dimensions, model functionality, etc.), designed their models, printed and presented their prototypes to peers for critique. After this, children returned to MaLT2 to digital iterate and/or make changes and/or corrections to their digital models based on feedback.

Figure 2: The 2D-models given to the children in MaLT2 at the beginning of the intervention

Data collection and analysis

The data collection sources used in this research are: i) Screen recordings of group work ii) Audio recording of the group discussions iii) Students' sketches iv) The digital files (.mlt) v) The 3D-printed artefacts and vi) Field notes. Data was triangulated and analysed using the method of critical incidents (Angelides, 2001), focusing on episodes where students collaboratively overcame challenges. As "critical" in this study we considered incidents that demonstrated the decisive role of tools (dynamic manipulation, 3D printing) and embodied schemas in shaping students' mathematical meanings and practices, in response to specific construction challenges that arose from their overarching goal to achieve Inscriptibility.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Critical Incident 1: Inscripting a circle in a square

Group 1 (consisted of students M1 and M2) decided to construct a cup holder with a square base on which a cylindrical receptacle would be developed (see Figure 3E). Their desire to inscribe a circle in the square that would form the basis of their cupholder-model, brought up the relative position of the centres of the two shapes and the relationship between the radius of the circle and the side of the square, as shown in their dialogue:

M2: We must put the centre of the one to be exactly on the centre of the other..

M1: Oh, we can achieve that first and then, try to have the radius to **reach**.. hmm.. the edge.. until the circle can **touch** the square (*he shows with his hands*)

M2: Then, the radius must be half of the side, huh?

M1: No..Why? Let's try 50 (*he proposes a random value for the radius*)

Through trial and error, the children attempted to achieve the desired result for the radius of the circle, but they failed so, they decided to introduce a variable for it. Dynamically manipulating the value of the radius length (by moving the slider) helped them confirm M2's initial hypothesis.

Figure 3: Sketches (3A, 3B), Digital Models (3C, 3D) and 3d printed model (3E)

Critical Incident 2: Inscribing a square in a circle

Group 7 (consisted of students M11 and M12) attempted to create a prototype for a cup holder with a hook to attach to the car dashboard. So, in their case, they faced the exact opposite challenge, namely inscribing a square into a circle, to create the “skeleton” of the cupholder. They decided not to use the given code and do it themselves.

M11: So, if we start from here (*points somewhere on the circle*).. and move.. let's say.. (*he pauses to think the length of the side of the square*) hmmm..

M12: Let's try 30, like the size of the radius.. (see Figure 4B).. oh no! It doesn't **reach** it.. we need to pull it a little further so that they **meet.. perfectly**..

M11: We try 5 more and see? (*they try randomly different values, but trial and error method fails*)

M11 suggests thinking about "*what they would see if they looked at it from above*". He draws the floor plan (see Figure 4Ci) and M12 gestures to indicate the turn the entity will make as soon as it reaches the circle.

M12: Oh!! So, let's find the angles... (*They are writing down the angles, see Figure 4Ci*)

M11: Look! These triangles are rectangular, aren't they? So,...Trigonometry!! We will find this..

They calculated the angles of each of the four right-angled triangles formed by the diagonals of the square (see Figure 4Ci) and expressed some trigonometric relationships (see Figure 4Cii). Soon, they found the appropriate relationship between the length of the side and the radius (see Figure 4D), corrected the code and continued, completing the inscription of the square in the circle with repetition loops for the rotation-moving forward set (see Figure 4E).

Figure 4: Sketch (4A), bugged digital model (4B), M11's floor plan (4Ci), Students' calculations (4Cii), Debugging (4D), Finalizing the digital model (4E) and 3d printed model (4F)

For both critical incidents presented above, Table 1 serves as an analytical tool that triangulates embodied elements (verbal descriptions and gestures), description of children's coding activity and their digital model to illustrate the dynamic interplay between students' embodied mathematical thinking elements and their digital constructions. It shall be read horizontally, with each row presenting the corresponding critical incident where these three elements informed each other to address each specific challenge.

ACTIVITY	EMBODIED ELEMENTS		CODING	DIGITAL MODEL
<i>Critical Incident 1:</i> INSCRIBING A CIRCLE IN A SQUARE	Verbal	Gestures	Coincident centers & Introduction of variable for the radius of the circle	
	<i>"fit exactly"</i> <i>"reach and touch</i> <i>the square..!"</i>	M2's gestures convey the contact of the circle with the side of the square Rough sketches [Figure 3A]		
	Verbal	Spatial visualization		
<i>Critical Incident 2:</i> INSCRIBING A SQUARE IN A CIRCLE	<i>"It doesn't reach it..</i> <i>"we need to pull it</i> <i>a little further so</i> <i>that they meet...</i> <i>perfectly.."</i>	M11 imagines and takes the initiative to draw the floor plan [Figure 4Ci]	Commands expressing trigonometric relationship between the length of the side of the square and the radius of the circle	

Table 1. Interplay of Embodied Elements, programming commands, and digital constructions

DISCUSSION

This pilot study investigated the dynamic creation of models inscribable in others, through textual programming and 3D printing. First findings demonstrate that models acted as "mathematical instruments" (Nemirovsky et al., 2020), synthesizing three dimensions: **1**) materiality, **2**) embodied practices: 2i) bodily actions (e.g., drawing a floor plan, hands' movement, gestures, etc), 2ii) verbal descriptions in spatial language and, **3**) semantic expressions (mathematical formalism in coding, expressing geometric relationships). In response to our second research question, our results inform on how the synergy and interrelation of these three dimensions intertwine and shape students' perceptuomotor activity when attempting to achieve Inscribability. A continuous, bidirectional, and dynamic interaction was observed between the embodied elements (gestures, phrases, sketches), the coding activity and the feedback that children were receiving from the tools. When inscribing the square in the circle for example, the children were gesturing intensely and discussing, simultaneously making sketches and returning to the code to edit it to materialize the mathematical object they had imagined, which they were trying to communicate with each other and/or the research team through gestures. They enacted bodily orientations (e.g., the idea of the floor plan) and gave meaning to symbols and relationships (e.g., from informal linguistic expressions to formal expressions of trigonometrical relationships) by awakening perceptual and motoric patterns through a process of mutual shaping, revealing how bodily action and mathematical practice are co-constituted. Multimodal reasoning—particularly students' gesture-coding coordination during dynamic manipulation—confirmed bodily action as constitutive of geometric understanding, extending prior DGE research (Pittalis & Drijvers, 2023) to programmable 3D environments.

Regarding our first research question, we note that the digital 3D modeling and printing tools integrated into this study functioned as bridges between the abstract idea of Inscribability and embodied experience. Especially, dynamic manipulation of digital models played a crucial role by "unveiling" hidden geometric co-dependencies, enhancing mathematical meaning-making and enriching the trajectory of the construction activity; gestures mirrored or, reversely, inspired on-

screen transformations and informed subsequent code refinements and computational decisions, such as that of the introduction of a variable for the radius of the circle. The contribution of 3D printing technology was significant yet admittedly limited to the tangible realm: it provided students with the prospect of physically materializing their models. However, it did not serve to validate their mathematical and/or computational choices; this function was primarily fulfilled by the dynamic manipulation within the programming environment itself.

Inscribability as a Conceptual Field emerges as a provocative geometric challenge and seems to open up fruitful opportunities for students to express and build new representations (digital, physical and mathematical) and to interconnect meanings in a holistic and dynamic way. Contrary to the "keychain syndrome" concerns regarding students' 3D-printing activity with little cognitive effort (Blikstein, 2013), here students engaged in deep mathematical work through computational construction. These findings demonstrate that when pedagogically scaffolded and framed, 3D printing and programming transcend superficial fabrication to enable qualitative exploration.

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REFERENCES

- Abrahamson, D., & Bakker, A. (2016). Making sense of movement in embodied design for mathematics learning. *Cognitive Research*, 1, 33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41235-016-0034-3>
- Alibali, M. W., & Nathan, M. J. (2011). Embodiment in mathematics teaching and learning: Evidence from learners' and teachers' gestures. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 21(2), 247–286. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2011.611446>
- Angelides, P. (2001). The development of an efficient technique for collecting and analyzing qualitative data: The analysis of critical incidents. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 14(3), 429–442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518390110029058>
- Arzarello, F., Olivero, F., Paola, D., et al. (2002). A cognitive analysis of dragging practises in Cabri environments. *Zentralblatt für Didaktik der Mathematik*, 34, 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02655708>
- Baccaglioni-Frank, A., & Mariotti, M. A. (2010). Generating conjectures in dynamic geometry: The maintaining dragging model. *International Journal of Computers for Mathematical Learning*, 15, 225–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-010-9169-3>
- Barab, S., & Squire, K. (2004). Design-based research: Putting a stake in the ground. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 13(1), 1–14. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327809jls1301_1
- Blikstein, P. (2013). Digital fabrication and 'making' in education: The democratization of invention. In J. Walter-Herrmann & C. Büching (Eds.), *FabLabs: Of machines, makers and inventors* (pp. 203–222). Transcript Publishers.

- Blum, W., & Niss, M. (1991). Applied mathematical problem solving, modelling, applications, and links to other subjects: State, trends and issues in mathematics instruction. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 22(1), 37–68. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3482238>
- de Freitas, E., & Sinclair, N. (2014). *Mathematics and the body: Material entanglements in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139600378>
- Drijvers, P. (2019). Embodied instrumentation: Combining different views on using digital technology in mathematics education. In U. T. Jankvist, M. van den Heuvel-Panhuizen, & M. Veldhuis (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Eleventh Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 8–28). Freudenthal Group & Freudenthal Institute. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02436279v1>
- Freudenthal, H. (1972). *Mathematics as an educational task*. Reidel.
- Kynigos, C. & Grizioti, M. (2018). Programming Approaches to Computational Thinking: Integrating Turtle Geometry, Dynamic Manipulation and 3D Space. *Informatics in Education*, 17(2), 321–340. <https://doi.org/10.15388/infedu.2018.17>
- Nemirovsky, R., Kelton, M. L., & Rhodehamel, B. (2013). Playing mathematical instruments: Emerging perceptuomotor integration with an interactive mathematics exhibit. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 44(2), 372–415. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5951/jresmetheduc.44.2.0372>
- Nemirovsky, R., Ferrara, F., Ferrari, G., et al. (2020). Body motion, early algebra, and the colours of abstraction. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 104, 261–283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-020-09955-2>
- Ng, O., & Chan, T. (2019). Learning as making: Using 3D computer-aided design to enhance the learning of shapes and space in STEM-integrated ways. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(1), 294–308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12643>
- Ng, O., & Ferrara, F. (2020). Towards a materialist vision of ‘learning as making’: The case of 3D Printing Pens in school mathematics. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18, 925–944. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-019-10000-9>
- Ng, O., & Ye, H. (2022). Mathematics learning as embodied making: Primary students’ investigation of 3D geometry with handheld 3D printing technology. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 23, 311–323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-022-09755-8>
- Pittalis, M., & Drijvers, P. (2023). Embodied instrumentation in a dynamic geometry environment: Eleven-year-old students’ dragging schemes. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 113(2), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-023-10222-3>
- Roth, W. M. (2016). Growing-making mathematics: A dynamic perspective on people, materials, and movement in classrooms. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 93, 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-016-9695-6>
- Roth, W. M., & Maheux, J. F. (2015). The stakes of movement: A dynamic approach to mathematical thinking. *Curriculum Inquiry*, 45(3), 266–284. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03626784.2015.1031629>
- Shvarts, A., Alberto, R., Bakker, A., Doorman, M., & Drijvers, P. (2021). Embodied instrumentation in learning mathematics as the genesis of a body-artifact functional system. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 107(3), 447–469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-021-10053-0>
- Vergnaud, G. (2009). The theory of conceptual fields. *Human Development*, 52(2), 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000202727>